

Speculation on Dirac Spinors Part II

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In Part I, we argued that the symmetry breaking of t and x for m_0 (rest mass) > 0 leads to a 2×2 identity matrix being assigned to t and a different 2×2 matrix with two eigenvalues being assigned to x (if one only assumes p in the x direction). We suggested that the two eigenvalues implied two dimensions perpendicular to the x -direction, namely y and z . These correspond to a basis of the 2×2 matrix linked with x .

The point we wish to make in this note, is that the above argument only requires two orthogonal basis vectors to define an x - y space. In other words, for the sake of argument, if one considered $(1,0)$ to be $y=1, z=0$ and $(0,1), y=0, z=0$, one may obtain a second set of relatively orthogonal co-ordinates by leaving $(1,0)$ alone, but writing $(0,-1)$. This represents the minimal angle (namely 180 degrees) one must rotate $(0,1)$ to get the new orthogonal representation. If the requirement is ONLY that one needs two orthogonal axes, then the two mentioned above are equally good. In other words, transforming from one to the other is like doing nothing or returning to a starting requirement so to speak, but "doing nothing" is usually linked with 360 degrees. Here it is only associated with 180 degrees because this is the rotation needed to get back to the starting requirement, namely two orthogonal co-ordinates.

The reason that the above argument is relevant is that one may show that if one has three 2×2 matrices linked with x, y, z , the z one has eigenvectors $(1,0), (0,1)$ (One could just as easily call the z one the x matrix as this is nomenclature. Traditionally, the z Pauli matrix has the eigenvectors $(1,0), (0,1)$). Furthermore, $\frac{1}{2} \hbar$ Pauli z matrix is said to be like L_z , the z -component angular momentum operator which is also the generator of rotations in the plane perpendicular to z . For usual rotations, 360 degrees means returning to the starting point, but for the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ case, the starting point means two orthogonal axes and so one would have to rotate $(0,1)$ by 720 degrees to return to its original position. In other words, the $\frac{1}{2} \hbar$ Pauli z -matrix linked with 360 degrees does rotate $(0,1)$ to $(0,-1)$ which represents an orthogonal axis with $(1,0)$, but this is not the same as bringing $(0,1)$ back to $(0,1)$. We suggest this as an explanation for the reason that $\frac{1}{2} \hbar$ Pauli requires 720 degrees for one to return to the original state, i.e. $(0,1)$ back to $(0,1)$.

Dirac and Pauli Matrices

As noted in Part I, Dirac matrices appear if one wishes to linearize:

$$E = \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} + m_0 c^2 \quad \text{with } E = i \hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \text{ and } \mathbf{p} = -i \hbar \nabla \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{i.e. } (i \hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} B + A \cdot (-i \hbar \nabla) + m_0 c^2) W(x,t) = 0 \quad ((2))$$

We argued that there is asymmetry between t and x and that in the rest frame a clock ticks and nothing else happens. A and B must be matrices and must anticommute. If one links nothing happening to t in the rest frame with an identity matrix, then the smallest is 2×2 . For

anti-commutation, one requires 4x4 matrices, with the overall form of the x,y,z ones being the same. In particular:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & sx \\ -sx & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & sy \\ -sy & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & sz \\ -sz & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad ((3))$$

The s_x, s_y, s_z matrices are the 2x2 Pauli matrices and have two distinct eigenvalues which we ascribed in Part I to represent two axes perpendicular to the momentum one. (For example, one might consider p as lying in the x direction. In that case, one needs to have a y and z axis even though momentum is only in the x .

The Meaning of the Requirement of Two Orthogonal Axes

We wish to stress in this note the meaning of having two orthogonal axes perpendicular to the direction of the p (momentum) vector. For p in the x direction, $(y=1, z=0)$ and $(y=0, z=1)$ and the set $(y=1, z=0)$ with $(y=0, z=-1)$ are equally good and represent the minimal rotation angle for $z=1$ to $z=-1$, i.e. 180 degrees. Thus, the condition to have two orthogonal axes means that to transform one set into the other does not mean that $(0,1)$ returns to $(0,1)$. Rather, it becomes $(0,-1)$, but the second set fulfills the requirement.

The reason we present the above argument is that the z Pauli matrix is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with eigenvectors } (1,0) \text{ and } (0,1) \quad ((4))$$

One may just as well call this the x matrix. (It is just a convention that it is called the z .)

When linearizing $E = pc + m_0 c^2$, one simply requires matrices which suffice. One does not worry about the link between the Pauli matrices and L_z , the z -angular momentum operator. As a result, there is initially no worry about $(0,1)$ transforming into $(0,-1)$ to go from one orthogonal set to another which is just as good and this being linked with only 180 degrees. Normally, one would like to have 360 degrees represent coming full circle.

If, however, one uses: $L_z = \frac{1}{2} \hbar \sigma_z$ Pauli z matrix as is traditionally done in the literature, then L_z is a generator of rotations about the z axis. Given $\frac{1}{2}$, an angle of 360 degrees becomes 180 degrees, just as in the above discussion. This transforms $(1,0), (0,1)$ to an equally good orthogonal set $(1,0), (0,-1)$, but does not bring $(0,1)$, back to itself which is what one usually considers 360 degrees to do. For this to happen one requires 720 degrees.

Thus, we argue that the purpose of the Pauli matrices is to create two orthogonal axis perpendicular to the momentum direction (p_x, p_y or p_z), but $(1,0), (0,1)$ is as good as $(1,0), (0,-1)$ and so identical sets as per the orthogonality requirement (i.e. one does not keep information about $(0,1)$ pointing to the right and $(0,-1)$ to the left means that a rotational degree of 180 suffices to create the transformation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Pauli matrices appear as part of Dirac matrices required in a linearized form of the Klein-Gordon equation. The 2x2 identity matrix is linked with t which is asymmetric to x . In the rest frame, only a clock ticks and so we suggest that this is the reason for considering the identity matrix linked to t . This leads to three 4x4 matrices for x, y, z containing anti-commuting 2x2 Pauli matrices.

We argued in Part I, that these have two eigenvalues and suggest two degrees of freedom. If one considers p lying in the x direction, then we argued that these represent two orthogonal axes perpendicular to x . Here we go further and suggest that $(1,0)$, $(0,1)$ and $(1,0)$, $(0,-1)$ are equally good representations of these two orthogonal axes, if orthogonality is the ONLY requirement. $(0,1)$ transforms to $(0,-1)$ through a rotation of 180 degrees, but one usually considers 360 degrees as returning one to an initial requirement. $(0,1)$ and $(0,-1)$ are not the same, but if one only considers orthogonality with $(1,0)$, then one cannot distinguish left and right directions.

We suggest that these arguments are relevant because $(1,0)$ and $(0,1)$ are the eigenvectors of the z -Pauli matrix (which may be called the x one. (Using z is just a convention). If one considers $L_z = .5 \hbar \sigma_z$ Pauli z matrix as being the generator of rotations about the z axis, then using 360 degrees as the angle means this is multiplied by $.5$ and behaves as 180 degrees. It is this 180 degrees, however, which transforms $(0,1)$ to $(0,-1)$ which still keeps it orthogonal with $(1,0)$. We suggest this is the reason for 720 degrees being required to return $(0,1)$ to $(0,1)$.